
A PATH TOWARDS AUTONOMOUS MACHINE INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) holds great promise for transforming medicine, yet current state-of-the-art models, including large language models, lack the reasoning and adaptability needed to fulfill this potential. We argue that world models grounded in active inference offer a strong foundation for clinical AI and propose diagnostic reasoning as an ideal conceptual testbed. We then outline essential features for AI inspired by human clinical reasoning and set research goals for building systems that move beyond pattern recognition toward trustworthy, explainable, and impactful machine intelligence in medicine.

Keywords Clinical Artificial Intelligence · Autonomous Machine Intelligence · Predictive Coding · Active Inference · World Models · Diagnostic Reasoning · Self-Supervised Learning · Cognitive Architecture · Generative Models · Joint Embedding Predictive Architecture

1 Introduction

Among all domains, the greatest benefits of artificial intelligence (AI) are anticipated in medicine. AI in medicine promises to improve disease diagnosis[1], enhance patient monitoring and risk prediction[2], support medical imaging analysis[3], aid clinical decision making[4], and personalize treatment strategies[5].

Recently, transformer architectures[6], together with large datasets and advances in computational infrastructure[7], have enabled the development of large language models (LLMs) that demonstrate impressive performance in answering clinical questions[8], solving complex cases with higher accuracy and lower cost[9] and enhancing clinical decision making[10].

However, LLMs act primarily as passive stateless static pattern recognizers, without reasoning or adaptive inference[11], are frozen at deployment[12], generalize poorly out of distribution often failing catastrophically on novel or underrepresented cases[13], lack metacognitive abilities such as confidence modulation[14], and hallucinate or confabulate by design[15], even after setting the temperature parameter to below zero[16].

As such, current state-of-the-art AI models—particularly LLMs—fail to exhibit core traits of intelligence required for diagnostic reasoning: understanding of the physical world, forming hypotheses, gathering evidence, persistence of memory, reasoning over time, confidence modulation, revising beliefs, and hierarchical planning[17, 5, 18, 19].

Therefore, If AI is to transform medicine, it must move beyond task-specific automation toward systems capable of autonomous machine intelligence. Task-based AI, even agentic, may offer short-term superficial utility, but it cannot serve as the foundation for generalizable and trustworthy clinical reasoning. Medicine needs AI models that simulate, anticipate, and reason within representations of the real clinical world.

In this perspective, we build upon recent shift in AI research[18] and propose that clinical AI offers a compelling testbed for developing dynamic world models building towards autonomous machine intelligence. We explore the theoretical potential of *active inference* as a framework for adaptive clinical reasoning systems. Using the cognitive workflow of a radiologist as a case study, we outline how such systems might operate in clinical practice. Finally, we discuss directions for future empirical research and implications for clinical AI.

2 Bayes' Rule, Active Inference, and Clinical Reasoning

Predictive coding, active inference, the Free Energy Principle, and Bayesian brain theories are interrelated mathematical frameworks grounded in Bayes' rule[20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29]:

$$P(H | D) = \frac{P(D | H) P(H)}{P(D)}$$

Bayes' rule describes how we update the probability of a hypothesis (H) in light of new data (D): the updated belief (the *posterior*, $P(H | D)$) is proportional to how likely the data are if the hypothesis were true (the *likelihood*, $P(D | H)$), weighted by the prior plausibility of the hypothesis (the *prior*, $P(H)$), and normalized across all possible hypotheses (the *evidence*, $P(D)$). For example, in radiology, let H be the hypothesis that a patient has lung cancer and D the observation of a suspicious nodule on CT. The prior probability $P(H)$ (disease prevalence) is updated by the likelihood $P(D | H)$ (chance of such a nodule if cancer is present) and normalized by the evidence $P(D)$ (overall frequency of such nodules), yielding the posterior $P(H | D)$, the updated probability of cancer given the CT finding. In this paper, we adopt *active inference* as our reference point while acknowledging its close relation to the broader Bayesian family.

3 Radiological Reasoning through the Lens of Active Inference

Physicians, in their clinical routine, rarely encounter diagnostic problems as blank slates or multiple choice questions. Instead, they enter the consultation with background knowledge and contextual cues (e.g. demographics, presenting complaint, prior history) that allow them to generate one or more working hypotheses. These hypotheses guide both interpretation and information gathering: further history, physical examination, or imaging studies are selected based on their predicted value in discriminating among candidate diagnoses. Moreover, physicians often make their decisions under uncertainty. The confidence with which a physician holds a hypothesis affects how they weigh new data. A confident prior may lead to disregarding conflicting evidence, while a weak prior invites broader exploration. In AI terms, this is the distinction between models that can reason about their confidence and those that cannot. Current AI systems are useless in this aspect as they typically produce point estimates or fixed probabilities without dynamically adjusting belief strength across time and context.

In a sense, as such, clinical reasoning is a form of *active inference*. It is an active, dynamic process of hypothesis generation, evidence gathering, and belief revision. Radiologists exemplify the structure of active inference in medicine [30]. When interpreting an image, they do not process it uniformly or compare it to a library of labeled exemplars. Nor do they collapse the image into a latent embedding and attempt to reconstruct the full input, as in LLMs, a strategy that risks distorting clinically relevant details by treating all pixels as equally meaningful. Instead, they use a structured internal model of normal and pathological anatomy to anticipate expected findings, attend to regions of interest, and infer likely causes of observed deviations. This process is generative and context-sensitive: given a clinical question (e.g. cough, trauma), the radiologist generates an internal simulation of what they expect to find, checks this against the image, and updates their hypotheses and confidence/uncertainty levels accordingly. Importantly, radiologists can generalize from relatively few cases. They do not need to see millions of labeled examples; instead, they acquire rich, structured knowledge that supports generalization to novel instances. This stands in contrast to current AI models, which are largely pattern matchers requiring massive data and performing poorly out-of-distribution. For illustration, see Figure 1.

4 Designing Autonomous Machine Intelligence in Medicine

Inspired by the diagnostic reasoning of a radiologist, an autonomous machine intelligence system in medicine must support inference over latent causes, not just mapping inputs to labels, but generating and updating beliefs about the hidden states that explain observed clinical findings. For example, new information, such as test results or imaging data, should trigger internal revision of hypotheses in real time, not merely produce new outputs from a frozen model. It must incorporate confidence modulation, the ability to represent and adjust uncertainty. A hallmark of truly knowledgeable

Figure 1: Radiologists’ image interpretation as an active inference process. Guided by the clinical question, radiologists form expectations about likely findings and use these to direct attention to the most informative areas of an image. They then compare what they observe against their expectations, revising their understanding and level of certainty as needed. This flexible, knowledge-driven approach allows them to adapt to new situations with relatively few prior examples—unlike most current AI systems, which depend heavily on large datasets and struggle outside their training domain.

physicians is not just their ability to generate diagnoses, but their ability to acknowledge when they do not know. Current AI systems rarely reason explicitly about confidence or uncertainty. Confidence in a hypothesis should guide how much weight is given to new evidence and which questions are asked next. It must support goal-directed data acquisition. Like a physician ordering the next test to resolve diagnostic ambiguity, the system should evaluate the expected information value of available actions and prioritize those that reduce uncertainty. It must maintain persistence of memory and context. This memory is critical for longitudinal reasoning and context-sensitive interpretation. It must provide transparent, structured reasoning. Rather than opaque outputs or post hoc rationalizations, it should expose its internal hypotheses, expected observations, prediction errors, and rationale for belief updates. This allows for intrinsic explainability, not added interpretability layers. It must minimize hallucinations. Because inference is grounded in structured internal models and belief updates are driven by evidence, predictions are epistemically constrained. Unlike LLMs, which often produce fluent but incorrect outputs, an adaptive world model is less likely to generate clinically implausible or dangerous responses. As such, we envision a model that begins with an internal prior, formed from background data, patient history, or presenting complaint, and generates predictions about expected findings. As evidence accumulates, prediction errors are computed, belief states are updated, and new predictions are generated. The system can selectively attend to new features, request additional data, and modulate its confidence throughout the process. In radiology, for example, the model might begin with the hypothesis that the patient has pneumonia. It predicts expected radiographic features (e.g., lobar consolidation), compares these to the observed image, and updates its internal belief if inconsistencies emerge. This recursive cycle continues until the model reaches a stable belief state or remains uncertain. Throughout, it maintains transparency in its reasoning steps and can explain why it believes what it believes. This architecture mirrors the cognitive structure of expert clinical reasoning.

5 Challenges and Future Directions

Even if suitable models were technically realizable, existing clinical datasets, evaluation metrics, and regulatory frameworks are the biggest challenge. Static benchmark tasks (e.g., multiple-choice questions or image classification) do not test dynamic inference, explainability, or robustness to distributional shift. There is an urgent need for new benchmark environments that simulate clinical reasoning as an interactive, multi-step task. Evaluation should reward not only accuracy, but also reasoning quality, uncertainty estimation, and decision traceability. Additionally, regulatory

guidance must evolve to accommodate models that update over time and behave more like reasoning agents than fixed-function tools.

5.1 Research goals

- Develop multi-modal self-supervised learning methods that can extract latent causal structure from real-world clinical data.
- Design architectures capable of representing and updating internal belief states.
- Explore mechanisms for uncertainty propagation and confidence-weighted attention.
- Build explainability directly into inference mechanisms, not as post hoc approximations.
- Construct interactive clinical benchmarks for dynamic reasoning under uncertainty.
- Engage with clinical, regulatory, and ethical stakeholders to build suitable datasets and guide responsible deployment.

6 Limitations

This work presents a conceptual perspective on the current state of clinical AI and the broader implications of shifting AI research toward models that incorporate clinical reasoning. However, it does not provide a proof of concept, nor does it offer a systematic review of existing models and frameworks that may align with, or be constructed upon, predictive coding or *active inference* principles. Future iterations of this work are planned to address these gaps. Moreover, the main argument relies on the assumptions of *active inference* as a potential framework mirroring cognitive processes in the human brain. While mathematically elegant and conceptually appealing, active inference remains one theoretical account among others of brain function and its neural underpinnings. Further work will be required to substantiate these claims and whether these models actually will pave the way towards better clinical AI.

7 Conclusion

Designing autonomous machine intelligence in medicine is not merely an academic exercise. It holds practical implications for the future of healthcare and AI development. A model capable of structured, transparent, and adaptive inference could support robust, explainable decision-making, generalize to rare or ambiguous cases, and operate safely in high-stakes clinical environments. It could also provide physicians with reasons, not just results, offering differential diagnoses and the rationale behind them, uncertainty levels, and expected discriminative findings. Radiology, pathology, dermatology, triage, and longitudinal care are promising initial domains. *Active inference* offers a principled theoretical framework for building clinical AI systems that simulate, predict, and revise. AI in medicine will only become trustworthy, explainable, and generalizable when it moves beyond memorization and toward systems that incorporate models of the world, not just patterns in the data.

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